

DIGITAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF SOUTH-EAST NIGERIA

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Abstract

Digital entrepreneurship is a key driver of economic growth, job creation, and innovation. Its success relies on entrepreneurial behavior, culture, strategies, and a strong innovation ecosystem supported by collaboration among governments, industries, businesses, educational institutions, and NGOs. Advancing digital technologies reshape traditional business models, foster innovation, and enhance operational efficiency. These advances enhance enterprise competitiveness, contributing to the broader competitiveness of both local and national economies. The transition of traditional economies into digital ones presents a significant opportunity for accelerated growth, particularly driven by small and medium-sized enterprises in the development of South East, Nigeria. This study aims to explore the impact of digital entrepreneurship on the development of the economy of South Eastern, Nigeria. This study is a conceptual review. The research is grounded in social network theory, social capital theory, and institutional theory to achieve its objectives. By reviewing existing literature, the study concludes that fostering a digital entrepreneurship culture is essential for a nation's economic progress in a globally competitive business environment. Among its recommendations, the study emphasizes that the Nigerian government should create a conducive business environment to support digital entrepreneurship and empower traditional entrepreneurs in their digital transformation journey.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Digital Entrepreneurship, Economic Development, South East, Nigeria.

Introduction

Entrepreneurship plays a critical role in job creation and poverty reduction, and its development should not be approached in isolation. Diverse strategies and methodologies are required to drive genuine economic growth and development, particularly in a country like Nigeria. Entrepreneurship development is a fundamental driver of economic growth in developing nations. According to Mladen (2018), entrepreneurs are not merely job seekers but job creators who stimulate the local economy by employing people, increasing purchasing power, and enhancing the standard of living. Their business activities engage local resources and firms, creating supply chain opportunities and channeling investments into local communities. This rise in entrepreneurial activity often leads to improvements in

infrastructure such as roads, water, and electricity that benefit the broader community (Nobanee, and Dilshad 2020).

Globally, there has been a significant focus on entrepreneurship development through academic research, education, seminars, and training programs aimed at fostering an entrepreneurial culture (Matlay, 2008). Fang and Alan (2016) emphasize the critical role of digital entrepreneurship as a pillar of economic growth, job creation, and innovation. They argue that a nation's capacity for digital entrepreneurship depends on entrepreneurial behavior, culture, strategies, and a supportive ecosystem that includes collaboration between governments, businesses, educational institutions, and NGOs.

The Nigerian government has a responsibility to economically empower its citizens, but it is unrealistic for any government to provide employment for all. Also, (Okarfor, 2018; Nobanee, and Dilshad 2020) suggests that introducing mandatory entrepreneurship education in schools is an effective strategy for empowering citizens. This is particularly relevant as digital entrepreneurship, a concept distinct from traditional entrepreneurship, emerges as a transformative force. According to Fang and Alan (2016), the European Commission (2013) identifies five key pillars in digital entrepreneurship: innovation, entrepreneurship, and digital ecosystems.

The evolution of globalization and digital technologies has shifted entrepreneurship to a digital level, resulting in changes to traditional business models and the creation of innovative products, services, and processes. This shift has significantly increased business competitiveness, benefiting both local and national economies. Mladen (2018) highlights that the digital economy contributes approximately 8% of GDP in G-20 countries, driving growth, empowerment, and job creation. Research in Europe shows that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) grow two to three times faster and create more jobs when digital technologies are integrated into their operations. The OECD (2012) defines the digital economy as one that facilitates the trade of goods and services through e-commerce on the internet.

Digital entrepreneurship has been conceptualized in various ways by scholars. Hence, Hull, Hung, and Hair (2006) described it as a subset of entrepreneurship where most activities are digitalized. Mladen (2018) defines digital entrepreneurship as value creation involving digital goods, services, distribution, and marketplaces. In the same light, Van Welsun (2016) sees it as the process of creating internet-enabled businesses, products, or services, while Davidson and Vaast (2010) view it as leveraging new media and internet technologies for business opportunities. Marc (2015) conceptualizes digital entrepreneurship as the pursuit of value generation through ICT-enabled products, processes, and markets.

New technologies are essential to digital entrepreneurship, serving as drivers of innovation and enabling businesses to achieve their objectives. Recent studies reinforce the significance of integrating digital

entrepreneurship into national development strategies, emphasizing its potential to transform economies and foster sustainable growth.

Statement of the Problem

Globalization has posed significant challenges for local entrepreneurs, who often struggle to compete in the global marketplace. One of the major hurdles faced by entrepreneurs in developing countries is adapting to the rapid influx of dynamic technologies in the business landscape. The digital economy is still evolving, and its impact on productivity will only become evident as digital technologies fully mature. However, industrialized nations are already experiencing a noticeable decline in productivity, sparking discussions about a potential productivity paradox in the digital economy (Gorelova, 2016). Meanwhile, digital entrepreneurship has introduced a highly flexible business environment, redefining traditional business models with innovations that disrupt established paradigms.

Objective of the Study

The central objective of this study is to examine digital entrepreneurship and economic development of Southeast Nigeria.

Literature Review

This study employs a comprehensive conceptual review, providing various perspective and understanding to concepts, and existing knowledge in order to guide the investigation.

Concept of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is fundamentally associated with business investment and the creation of wealth. Killby (1971) defines entrepreneurship as an individual's willingness and ability to identify investment opportunities, establish enterprises, and operate them profitably. In this context, profitability is a critical factor for business growth, sustainability, and wealth generation. Ndubuisi (2013) highlights entrepreneurship as a key driver of development and economic empowerment, achieved through effective investment, coordination of production factors, and risk management by the entrepreneur, who acts as a human catalyst.

A primary responsibility of the entrepreneurial catalyst is risk management, emphasizing calculated risk-taking. Decisions to pursue business opportunities and other critical actions are based on objective evaluations of variables that enhance business success. Abgaeze (2007) characterizes entrepreneurship as leveraging unmet needs to create wealth by mobilizing and investing resources, accepting associated

financial and psychological risks, and reaping the rewards of such ventures. As Ndubuisi (2013) notes, entrepreneurship thrives on creating and adding value, investing capital, consolidating resources, managing uncertainty, and deriving both material and psychological fulfillment.

Concept of Digital Entrepreneurship

Hull, Hung, and Hair (2006) define digital entrepreneurship as a subset of entrepreneurship where some or all elements that would traditionally be physical in a conventional organization have been digitized. Mladen (2018) suggests that digital entrepreneurship involves creating new value through digital goods or services, digital distribution, digital workplaces, digital marketplaces, or a combination of these elements. He further explains that digital entrepreneurial activities depend on information technology to create markets, distribute, transform, or perform services.

Van Welsum (2016) views digital entrepreneurship as the process of establishing a new or innovative business, product, or service that is enabled or delivered via the internet. Mladen (2018) asserts that this definition applies not only to start-ups introducing new digital products or services but also to the digital transformation of existing business activities within firms or the public sector. Davidson and Vaast (2010) describe digital entrepreneurship as the pursuit of new opportunities offered by new media and internet technologies, arguing that without these technologies, digital entrepreneurs would struggle to deliver products or services effectively. In some cases, the business model itself might not even exist without information technology.

Jean-Michael and Frederic (2019) conceptualize digital entrepreneurship as the entrepreneurial creation of digital value, supported by various socio-technical digital enablers that facilitate the effective acquisition, processing, distribution, and consumption of digital information. They note that this concept can be applied to specific business types, including newly established ventures and digitally self-reliant businesses. These enablers help support the entire process of new venture creation, from idea generation and opportunity recognition to intellectual property protection, production, marketing, and distribution. Steiniger (2019) highlights that technologies like social media, open-source software and hardware, crowdsourcing, crowdfunding, e-trust, online reputation assessment, 3D printing, digital imaging, and big data are empowering aspiring entrepreneurs by significantly reducing the barriers between invention and the creation of new companies. According to European Commission (2015) as cited in Jean-Micheal and Frederic (2019), *“Digital entrepreneurship embraces all new ventures and the transformation of existing businesses that drive economic and/or social value by creating and using novel digital technologies. Digital enterprises are characterized by a high intensity of utilization of novel digital*

technologies (particularly social, big data, mobile and cloud solutions) to improve business operations, invent new business models, sharpen business intelligence, and engage with customers and stakeholders. They create the jobs and growth opportunities of the future”

Steininger (2019) argues that Information and Communication Technology (ICT) plays four key roles in digital entrepreneurial operations. These roles include acting as a facilitator that simplifies the operations of start-ups, serving as a mediator for the activities of new businesses, being an outcome of entrepreneurial efforts, and functioning as a ubiquitous enabler of new digital business models. However, Steininger emphasizes that the analysis of digital entrepreneurship cannot be reduced merely to the integration of ICT into traditional entrepreneurship.

The Digitalization of Entrepreneurial Processes

Nambisan (2016) asserts that the dynamic and fluid nature of innovation has made entrepreneurial processes more flexible compared to those in traditional economies. As a result, entrepreneurial processes now follow progressive and nonlinear paths, facilitated by digital tools and platforms. The digitalization of entrepreneurship has helped break down the boundaries between different stages of the entrepreneurial process, thereby reducing the barriers between invention and innovation (Anderson, 2014; Steiniger, 2019 in Jean-Michael and Frederic, 2019). According to Jean-Michael and Frederic (2019), recent studies on digital entrepreneurship have shifted focus from identifying the phases of entrepreneurship to exploring how entrepreneurs can scale their ideas into viable businesses. These studies emphasize the use of digital technologies to support opportunity recognition, ideation, idea validation, testing, and the design of effective business models.

Scholars such as Huang et al. (2017) highlight three key mechanisms that enable rapid scaling: (i) data-driven operations, (ii) instant release, and (iii) swift transformation. They stress the interaction of these mechanisms in accelerating the scaling of digital ventures. This aligns with the views of Srinivasan and Venkatraman (2018), who argue that entrepreneurial success is closely linked to the actions of other entrepreneurs and is coordinated within and across platforms. Le Dinh et al. (2018) further explore how digital entrepreneurs can strategically navigate the complex digital landscape, and how their decisions influence the entrepreneurial process and overall success.

Importance of Digital Entrepreneurship

Nigeria exhibits the characteristics of a mono-economy, with a modern sector heavily reliant on oil revenues, overlaying a traditional agriculture and trading economy (Ndubuisi, 2013). It has been noted that effective economic development cannot be achieved without addressing both traditional and digital

entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship spans all aspects of human activity, functioning as an art, a cultural necessity, and a science focused on the production of goods and services to meet social, economic, and human needs.

Chigbo (2008) emphasizes that entrepreneurship is fundamental to an economy, observing that prosperous nations prioritize its development and exploitation to support their growing populations, generate revenue for development, and provide employment. This, in turn, helps reduce social crimes, corruption, and other forms of indiscipline that hinder economic progress. Jean-Micheal and Frederic (2019) argue that digital entrepreneurship can revitalize the declining manufacturing sector, boost output, support import substitution, and accelerate the achievement of food security, self-sufficiency, and national self-reliance. Fang and Alan (2016) contend that a country's digital entrepreneurial capacity is largely shaped by digital entrepreneurial behavior, culture, strategies, and a supportive innovation ecosystem where governments, industries, businesses, educational institutions, and non-governmental organizations collaborate effectively. In the same line of thought, Murphy et al. (2005) in Fang and Alan (2016) posit that; *“it is primarily entrepreneurship that has been responsible for the amazing increase in Western per capita income over the past 200-300 years. The continuing importance of entrepreneurship in Australia is demonstrated by Hendrickson et al. (2015) that the increase in employment that occurred during the Global Financial Crisis, the greatest economic downturn since the Great Depression of the 1930s, was attributable to entrepreneurship”*.

Supporting this perspective, Zahra (1999) argued that entrepreneurship plays a critical role in socio-economic development by addressing unemployment, offering a wider range of consumer products, and enhancing competitiveness and overall prosperity. Many countries' economic progress has been aligned with this concept. For example, Fang and Alan reported that the rapid growth of ICT and digital technologies has had a significant impact on Australia's economy. The direct contribution of the internet to the Australian economy is estimated at \$50 billion, or 3.6% of GDP (AIIA, 2015). Research has also shown that, in 2015, 10% of job vacancies in Australia were in the ICT sector. Additionally, Australian studies reveal that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) that actively embrace new technologies to enhance communications and business processes generate more jobs and revenue compared to SMEs with limited technological adoption. Specifically, between 2010 and 2012, technology-leading SMEs increased revenues 15 percentage points faster and created jobs at twice the rate of less progressive companies. A recent PWC analysis predicts that Australian small businesses could generate an additional \$49.2 billion in revenue over the next decade by more effectively leveraging digital technologies, with 53% of this growth coming from rural and regional areas (PWC Australia, 2015).

This data underscores the significance of promoting digital entrepreneurship for the Australian economy (Fang and Alan, 2016).

Similarly, for South East, Nigeria to achieve its goal of becoming a leading global digital economy by 2030, it is essential for the country to develop a national strategy and concerted efforts to cultivate digital entrepreneurship. This will be crucial for driving the digital economy and maximizing the business potential of digital technologies.

Theoretical Framework

This study employed Social Network Theory, Social Capital Theory, and Institutional Theory as its theoretical framework to effectively address the study's objectives.

Social Network Theory

Jacob Moreno is credited with creating the first sociograms in the 1930s to examine interpersonal relationships. These methods were later formalized in the 1950s, and by the 1980s, social network theories and methodologies became widely adopted within the social and behavioral sciences. Social Network Theory focuses on the interactions between individuals, organizations, or groups within their network. Understanding the theory becomes easier when examining its components, starting with the broadest element, networks, and progressively narrowing down to the smallest unit, the actor.

Social Capital Theory

Bourdieu and Coleman are recognized as the founding theorists of Social Capital, as they introduced the concept systematically for the first time, though independently and nearly simultaneously. Social Capital Theory asserts that social relationships serve as valuable resources that contribute to the development and accumulation of human capital. From an evolutionary standpoint, social capital can be understood as the aspect of social relationships that generates reproductive benefits. Social capital is categorized into three types: bonding social capital, bridging social capital, and linking social capital. It is essential because it represents the productive benefits derived from sociability, as shared values, norms, trust, and belonging facilitate social exchange. Our society, economy, institutions, and political systems would not function without social capital.

Institutional Theory

Developed by theorists such as Meyer and Rowan, and DiMaggio and Powell, Institutional Theory posits that the institutional environment has a significant influence on the formation of formal structures within

organizations, often more so than market pressures. This theory examines the deeper, more enduring aspects of social structure, focusing on how rules, norms, and routines become established as authoritative guidelines for social behavior. The institutional approach refers to strategies used by organizations that have been proven effective in achieving specific goals or objectives. According to Institutional Theory, institutional forces are multifaceted, as summarized by Scott (1995) in Fang and Alan (2016), and can be categorized into regulatory, social, and cultural influences that promote an organization's survival and legitimacy. These institutional forces can be both formal, such as laws and regulations, and informal, including social norms, values, and beliefs. While Institutional Theory has been widely applied in entrepreneurship research (Bruton et al., 2010), its application in digital entrepreneurship is relatively new. Fang and Alan (2016) suggest that the lens of Institutional Theory allows for an in-depth exploration of how societal regulations, rules, social norms, and culture can shape the ecosystem in which digital entrepreneurship can flourish.

Empirical Review

Fang and Alan (2016) conducted a theoretical study on “Digital Entrepreneurship: Research and Practice”, which aimed to explore the emerging concept of digital entrepreneurship from multiple disciplinary perspectives. These included information technology and systems, entrepreneurship and management, as well as the political, legal, and socio-economic factors that impact it. The study developed a conceptual model for examining digital entrepreneurship, drawing on current literature and three well-established theories—social network theory, social capital theory, and institutional theory. The model addresses five key research questions about digital entrepreneurship, providing a deeper understanding of its concept and practical applications.

Jean-Micheal and Frederic (2019) carried out a study titled “The Age of Digital Entrepreneurship.” The study aimed to offer a new perspective on digital entrepreneurship, focusing on digital information processing and the creation of digital value at the firm level. This approach was integrated with existing research on digital entrepreneurship in Digital Platforms. The study provided a relational, technologically deterministic, and collective view of digital entrepreneurship, using a digital processing framework to model and describe entrepreneurial actions mediated by or enacted through digital technologies. The authors suggested that this perspective could lead to significant developments in the field and recommended increased attention to the potential for the digital divide in digital entrepreneurship. This gap, referring to the disparity in digital skills and knowledge among entrepreneurs, is essential for developing policies and programs that support firms and boost overall competitiveness in the global digital economy.

Mladen (2018) studied the importance of digital entrepreneurship in economic development. The aim of the study was to assess the role of digital technologies in business growth and development, emphasizing their significance for local development and the strengthening of national economies. The study reviewed existing literature and found that digital technologies transform business models, introduce new products and services, and enhance business process efficiency, thus making enterprises more competitive. These changes also contribute to the competitiveness of local and national economies. The digital economy in the European Union, for example, grew much faster than the broader economy, leading to job creation and the continued digital transformation of the European economy.

Marc (2015) investigated the barriers and drivers of digital entrepreneurship. The report examined the concept of digital entrepreneurship and evaluated 18 current measurement frameworks that support empirical analysis of entrepreneurship, its determinants, performance, and impacts. The report identified the strengths and weaknesses of existing frameworks for addressing digital entrepreneurship and proposed several ways forward. These included enhancing entrepreneurial education and training, creating environments that support the growth of entrepreneurs, developing role models, and reaching out to underrepresented groups with entrepreneurial potential. Other recommendations included improving access to finance, providing support during critical phases of the business lifecycle, fostering new business opportunities in the digital age, facilitating business transfers, creating second chances for honest entrepreneurs after bankruptcy, and reducing regulatory burdens.

In an investigation into the “Role of ICT for Entrepreneurship Development in Nigeria”, Sulaiman, et. al. (2020) submits that a significant number of young graduates in many African countries face uncertainty regarding job prospects, with self-employment emerging as a potential solution to this challenge. However, such an approach requires the development of entrepreneurship skills. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) should be regarded as a crucial tool for accelerating the growth of entrepreneurship programs in Nigeria. This article explored the role of ICT in Nigeria’s entrepreneurial development. It highlights challenges such as frequent power outages, a lack of skilled technicians, limited insurance options, emergencies, and uncertainties that entrepreneurs must overcome. The article also suggested that the government should subsidize ICT imports to reduce costs and help entrepreneurs sustain their businesses. Additionally, the government is encouraged to provide health insurance for ICT entrepreneurs in case of injuries, fraud, or natural disasters.

Methodology

This study employs a desk review approach to examine digital entrepreneurship and economic development of Southeast Nigeria. The methodology involved an extensive literature review, sorting

and gathering relevant information from academic articles, journals, books, reports and reputable paper and online sources.

Findings

Digital Entrepreneurship and Economic Development of South Eastern Nigeria

Digital entrepreneurship has the potential to play a transformative role in the economic development of Southeastern Nigeria, a region that has historically been characterized by agriculture, trade, and informal business practices. In the contemporary global economy, digital technologies have reshaped how businesses operate, interact with consumers, and scale. These changes present a unique opportunity for the region to leapfrog traditional challenges and embrace the potential of a digital economy (Sulaiman, et. al. 2020).

Digital entrepreneurship encompasses the development of new business models, products, and services that primarily rely on the digital environment to function, market, and deliver value to customers (Mladen, 2018; Jean-Micheal & Frederic, 2019). In Southeastern Nigeria, where small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are central to the economy, digital entrepreneurship can facilitate improved business processes, increased access to markets, and the creation of new jobs. The digital economy in Nigeria, according to Fang and Alan (2016), has the potential to significantly contribute to the nation's economic growth. The country has witnessed an increasing adoption of digital technologies, especially among young entrepreneurs, many of whom are turning to the internet and mobile devices to develop innovative business solutions. For the Southeastern region, characterized by high entrepreneurial activity, digital entrepreneurship can create new opportunities in sectors such as e-commerce, digital marketing, software development, fintech, and education technology.

Specifically, economic opportunities through digital entrepreneurship can affect the southeast region are;

Job Creation

As highlighted by Mladen (2018), digital entrepreneurship is a major driver of job creation, especially in emerging economies. With the adoption of digital tools, small businesses can scale operations faster, reach a broader customer base, and generate more employment opportunities. In Southeastern Nigeria, this can help address the high unemployment rates and reduce youth migration to urban centers.

Enhanced Productivity and Efficiency

The digitalization of business processes leads to greater efficiency and productivity, which is essential for economic development. Small businesses in Southeastern Nigeria can utilize digital platforms for

inventory management, customer service, and financial transactions, thereby reducing costs and improving service delivery (Marc, 2015). Digital technologies can help businesses streamline operations, making them more competitive in both local and global markets.

Access to Global Markets

One of the most significant advantages of digital entrepreneurship is its ability to break down geographical barriers. Businesses in Southeastern Nigeria can utilize e-commerce platforms, social media, and digital marketing tools to access international markets, promoting their products to a global audience. This access is crucial for economic diversification, as it allows regional businesses to tap into markets outside traditional sectors such as agriculture and informal trading (Jean-Micheal & Frederic, 2019).

Improvement in Service Delivery

Digital entrepreneurship can also improve service delivery in key sectors such as education, healthcare, and finance. For example, digital platforms can be used to deliver educational content to rural communities, improving literacy rates and the employability of young people. Similarly, digital platforms can provide access to financial services for underserved populations, helping to reduce financial exclusion and promote inclusive economic growth (Fang & Alan, 2016).

Challenges to Digital Entrepreneurship in Southeastern Nigeria

Despite the promising potential of digital entrepreneurship, several challenges hinder its full realization in Southeastern Nigeria.

Inadequate Infrastructure

According to Mladen (2018), one of the main barriers to digital entrepreneurship is the lack of reliable and affordable infrastructure. In many parts of Southeastern Nigeria, poor internet connectivity, frequent power outages, and limited access to digital devices make it difficult for entrepreneurs to fully leverage digital technologies. The government must invest in improving digital infrastructure, especially in rural areas, to support the growth of digital businesses.

Limited Digital Literacy

Another challenge identified by Fang and Alan (2016) is the low level of digital literacy among many entrepreneurs in the region. Digital entrepreneurship requires a certain level of digital skills, and without proper training programs, many potential entrepreneurs may find it difficult to navigate the digital

landscape. There is a need for targeted capacity-building programs that equip entrepreneurs with the skills necessary to thrive in a digital economy.

Access to Finance

Financing is often a significant obstacle for small and medium enterprises in Nigeria, particularly in the context of digital entrepreneurship. Traditional banks are often reluctant to lend to new businesses in the digital space due to perceived risks. A lack of access to venture capital and angel investors also makes it difficult for digital startups to scale their operations. As recommended by Marc (2015), there is a need for government and financial institutions to provide funding and create a supportive environment for digital businesses.

Regulatory Environment

The regulatory environment in Nigeria can sometimes stifle the growth of digital entrepreneurship. Inadequate or outdated policies related to digital business operations, taxes, and intellectual property rights can create uncertainty for digital entrepreneurs. There is a need for policymakers to create and implement clear, business-friendly regulations that encourage digital entrepreneurship while protecting consumers and ensuring fair competition.

Role of Government and Policy Makers

To foster the growth of digital entrepreneurship in Southeastern Nigeria, the government must play an active role in creating a conducive environment for digital businesses. As noted by Nambisan (2016), digital entrepreneurship requires policies that promote the adoption of digital technologies, enhance digital skills, and create access to finance. The government should invest in digital infrastructure, provide incentives for technology adoption, and offer training programs to equip entrepreneurs with the necessary skills.

Moreover, the government should implement policies that encourage the development of a supportive innovation ecosystem. According to Fang and Alan (2016), a thriving digital economy requires collaboration between governments, businesses, educational institutions, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). By fostering a culture of innovation, the government can stimulate the growth of digital startups, promote job creation, and drive regional economic development.

Conclusion

Digital entrepreneurship holds significant promise for the economic development of Southeastern Nigeria. By leveraging digital technologies, entrepreneurs in the region can enhance productivity, access new markets, and create employment opportunities. However, challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, low digital literacy, and limited access to finance must be addressed. With the right policy interventions and support from government and private institutions, Southeastern Nigeria can harness the full potential of digital entrepreneurship to drive sustainable economic growth. It is essential for governments and political leaders to prioritize encouraging SMEs to integrate modern digital technologies into their daily operations to fully harness the social and economic benefits.

The Federal Republic of Nigeria should recognize the digital economy as a fundamental and strategic component of its overall economic framework, aiming to establish favorable conditions for enhancing policy frameworks, institutional support, employment benefits, and financing initiatives that promote entrepreneurship within the digital and global economy. Providing affordable and reliable infrastructure, particularly in rural communities, is a critical step toward eliminating barriers to business operations and enabling digital entrepreneurs to unlock their full economic potential. By engaging in digital entrepreneurship, entrepreneurs contribute to job creation, GDP growth, increased exports, and an improved standard of living across the country. New businesses within the digital economy hold even greater potential for growth, amplifying these positive impacts.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from the literature review, we recommend the following:

1. Traditional entrepreneurs should make concerted efforts to transform existing products, services, and business models into digital formats.
2. The Nigerian government should intensify efforts to enhance policy frameworks, improve technical skills, develop programs, and facilitate access to finance for initiatives supporting digital entrepreneurship. The primary goal of these efforts is to boost competitiveness, attract investment, and create employment opportunities.
3. Technologies should be leveraged by existing and traditional businesses to digitally transform their operations across all areas. Entrepreneurs who fail to adapt to the transformation process risk losing their competitive edge and may face negative consequences.
4. Entrepreneurship research in the digital economy should expand to incorporate literature from other disciplines, such as political science, marketing, and information systems. Drawing from

political science literature is essential for understanding digital governance, digital citizenship, and their significance in digital entrepreneurial ecosystems.

5. Research on entrepreneurship should continue to focus on the systemic characteristics of the digital economy that enable digital entrepreneurship, moving beyond a narrow focus on high-impact, high-potential, and high-growth businesses.
6. Digital entrepreneurship research should explore the inner workings of users in the process of consuming and creating digital information. Understanding how entrepreneurial agents can extract and capture value from users is essential, making insights into consumer psychology and social psychology crucial in the digital economy.

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